

SYNONYM PHRASEOLOGISMS IN THE COGNITIVE PARADIGM

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The article deals with the issue of the status of synonymous phraseological units in the cognitive paradigm. Since cognitive linguistics is a new branch of modern linguistics, research in this area is very relevant. In this study, the author considers synonymous phraseological units based on the language material of the Azerbaijani language. It also analyzes the term "concept" in the background of cognitive science.

Keywords: cognitive, concept, synonym, phraseological units, linguistics.

Introduction

The main goal of cognitivism is the recognition of mass public consciousness in language. The phraseological units we use in language reflect any concept. Concepts such as "death, life, love, hate, war, peace, good, bad, good, evil" play a special role in the formation of phraseological units in the modern Azerbaijani language, including the synonymous line.

"In some cases, the first main meaning of a lexeme actually turns out to be a derivative meaning. The previous meaning of such a lexeme is forgotten and the etymological meaning becomes two old meanings. Lexical meanings are further grouped into both literal and figurative meanings. The general lexical meaning of a lexeme is usually the correct meaning. Derivative meaning is usually portable. The image that is based on the transfer of meaning can be extinguished and forgotten. However, such a meaning is still considered a portable meaning. For example, leg of the table. Lexical meaning is also distinguished as (nominative) meaning and figural (figurative) meaning. For example, key — (key of the lock — nominative meaning (open) key of the knowledge figural meaning. Nominative meaning is a lexical meaning that serves as the name of something character or action. Nominative meaning is directly related to reality. Figural meaning serves to create figurative. The figural meaning is sometimes the same as the nominative meaning." [Tadjiyeva: 2021, 158].

Method and Materials

In the course of the study, descriptive and descriptive-comparative methods of linguistics were used. The material of the study is the linguistic facts and materials of the Azerbaijani language.

Results

Concepts mainly reflect polar categories. The most commonly used concepts are: *light - dark, sky - earth, right - left, up - down, life - death*, etc. These polar categories include *nature - culture, activity - passivity, rationality - irrationality, spirit - matter, authority - subordination*, etc.

The concept has a national cultural character. Linguistic features of the language are reflected in the concept. Since each phraseological unit also reflects the ethnolinguistic features of the people, the terms concept and phraseology are closely related to each other and there is a close relationship between them. The concept is also indicative of ethnic thinking.

The concept reflects the national, cultural experience of the people. Often the concept is equated with the concept. However, a subtle nuance should be noted here. The concept and meaning are universal, and the concept includes specific national, cultural characteristics.

In general, "concept" is a notion related to culture, and it consists of conceptual signs, i.e., separate signs of the objective and subjective world, which are differently reflected in the mind, differing in the degree of abstraction. As a result of research conducted in the field of cognitive linguistics, it can be described the relevant concept as an element of the national conceptosphere.

Phraseologisms, as concepts, are directly related to the national, cultural ideas of the people. The language mapping of the world is presented in the system of concepts. In fact, behind of all lexical units there is a concept. However, the concept is reflected more prominently in phraseological units and paremiological constructions. Each phraseological unit is a linguistic sign, but also has a conceptual essence. At first glance, we perceive the phraseological unit as a conventional language sign. Even so this does not reduce the conceptual essence of the phraseological unit.

The conceptual essence of the phraseological unit is the expression of the people's consciousness in language. We can express our opinion in another way, "According to existing ideas, language units, mainly words activate concepts in the brain during the process of the recipient's understanding of the text. Activating concepts is bringing them into a state of awareness so that they can be used in the future. If the recipient determines the characteristics of the relationships between separate concepts and combines them within a single system of meanings, the text is perceived as coherent as a whole" [Abdullayev: 2011, 89].

The concepts reflected in the national phraseology are directly related to the customs of the people, the national ethnic outlook. When talking about the cognitive basis of a phraseological unit, it is necessary to correctly understand and explain the relationship between phraseological semantics and the concept. The conceptual basis of each phraseological unit appears within the text and in the speech process. The concept creates the semantic foundation of the phraseological unit as a whole. In the national consciousness, any

features of the object are conceptualized and this is accepted as a national, cultural fact.

Any specific feature of the concept, which is a national, cultural fact, is reflected in the process of phraseologisation. That is, "The phraseological unit attracts attention as a fairly complex type of sign from this point of view. As a secondary nominative unit, the phraseological unit reflects the disproportional nature of the language code. However, one aspect should be taken into account here. When we talk about the disproportionality of language (in fact, the sign and therefore the system of signs), we still prefer structural views. However, it should be taken into account that this disproportion reflects the associative character of human thinking and the nature of human psychology. From this point of view, cognitive analysis continues structural analysis" [Babashova: 2016, 34].

Concepts must be verbalized so that we can understand what is being said. Phraseological units are one of the important indicators of conceptualization. The concept covers the entire language system and is even represented in the national folklore system. The concept is not only reflected in the language. The concept is reflected in all areas of national culture. Language is also the brightest indicator of culture, as well as national thinking and national mind.

The phraseological system of the language does not fully reflect the conceptual system of the people's consciousness. The notion of concept, conceptual system is much wider and comprehensive than the phraseological system. Phraseology is only part of the indicators of the conceptual system. Phraseological units also reflect the associative mechanism of national mind.

According to L. Weisgerber, natural languages differ from a conceptual point of view. Of course, the conceptual system of the language should not be confused with the internal form. The internal form refers only to the image basis of the semantic system. The actual meaning can be conditioned by the internal form only to one degree or another, it cannot fully determine it [Weisgerber: 2009, p. 97].

"Hence, the concepts of lexical meaning are not equal to semema. Moreover, in a polysemous lexeme, each lexical meaning has its own lexical context, and each lexical meaning may also be different in its grammatical nature. It should also be noted that each lexical meaning can be distinguished by its methodological semantics as a specific feature, it is possible to enter into a synonymous relationship, an antonymic relationship, a new lexeme is formed from each lexical meaning. If a lexeme is unambiguous, the above character properties are equivalent to a lexeme, and such a lexeme is considered to be equivalent to a language unit (lexical unit)." [Tadjiyeva: 2021, 160].

A concept must be verbalized, but it is more complex than a lexical unit. That is why the concept is not equal to the lexical unit. The fact that the concept is not the same as the lexical unit and does not overlap, indicates the richness of the concept. Since the concept is a mental entity, it does not coincide with the lexical unit.

That is, according to the cognitive approach, the creation of speech is viewed as a thinking process, which at the same time considers cognitive and language structures in their constant, joint activity and integration. But for this reason, it requires not only operational mechanisms in the human brain, but also a special "stationary" basis for its application. But it is possible to look at the study of human speech and the historical perspective as a result of its development. This is especially important for linguistics, because the influence of the human factor on language is already clearly visible in the process of language formation.

A number of new concepts play an important role for cognitive linguistics. For example, linguists have always used the concepts of folk mind and psychology. In the analysis of lexicon and phraseology, when thinking about paremiological units and proverbs, the direct connection of these language units with culture and mass minds of the people was always emphasized. However, modern cognitive linguistics generally values language, its systemic nature and structure as a direct result of thinking. Concepts such as conceptual system, categorization, mentality and cognitive base play a key role in this new intellectual space. Phraseological units involved in cognitive analysis should be interpreted based on the methods and principles of system-structural linguistics. In other words, cognitive analysis should not be done in isolation.

"Phraseological synonyms are phraseological units that, denoting the same concept and being stylistically homogeneous or heterogeneous, clarify, reveal, emphasize new features, new aspects and shades of the designated concept. Similar phraseological units arose on the basis of different images." [Nurgalina: 2014, 83].

Each line that creates phraseological synonymy in the modern Azerbaijani language actually reflects a certain concept. For example, the concept of God/Allah, which exists in Turkish languages, is reflected in such synonymous phraseology. *Allah deməyincə, bəndə nə edə bilər//Allah öldürməyəni kimsə öldürə bilməz* (No one can kill what God does not kill). In this line, it is reflected in the mind of the mass, society that God is a force and being capable of every power. The concept of good and bad in these units as *Armudun yaxşısını ayı yeyər// Keçinin qoturu bulağın gözündən su içər* (an unworthy person's claim is great); In the language, the concept of fear manifests itself in synonymous phraseological units such as *canına üşütmə düşmək – ürək-köbəyi düşmək* (ürək – göbəyini yemək) – *bağrı yarılmaq – bədənini vahimə bürümək* (to be afraid). The concept of poverty is reflected in the synonymous line of *qəpiyə güllə atmaq// cibində siçan oynamaq* (to be poor).

The presence of a shade of meaning or additional meaning helps to semantically clearly distinguish one synonymous phraseological unit from another and choose the most accurate one.

"Phraseological meanings, as in lexical meanings, are nomoen in a specific context. Just as in lexemes, if a phrase is unambiguous, it is a linguistic unit (equiva-

lent to a phraseological unit). If a phrase is polysemantic, each of its phrases will have its own linguistic unit (equivalent to a separate phraseological unit), because, as in lexemes, each phrase has its own lexical content (collection of ideographic semantics), with its own methodical (emotional expressive) semantics." [Tadjiyeva: 2021, 160].

Conclusion

All considered phraseological units are synonymous, close in meaning, but this does not always make it possible to replace one phraseological unit with another, which is explained by their inherent semantic or stylistic nuances.

In choosing from the group of synonymous phraseological units one, the most accurate, indispensable in this context, the author's ability to see the semantic or expressive-stylistic shades of similar phraseological units is manifested.

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